

Transformative Approaches to Teaching and Learning Civic Education: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

Chanda Chansa Thelma

Chreso University, Lusaka, Zambia, Department of Humanities and Social Sciences
Email Address: tchanda@chresouniversity.edu.zm

Abstract:

Overview: Transformative approaches to teaching and learning civic education emphasize active, participatory methods that empower students to engage critically with social and political issues. This study was carried out in Lusaka district, the capital city of Zambia.

Body of Knowledge: Transformative approaches move beyond traditional rote learning to foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative skills. They incorporate experiential learning opportunities, such as community service, simulations, and debates, which allow students to connect theoretical knowledge with real-world applications.

Methods: The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. The study was conducted in 5 selected secondary schools of Lusaka district, targeting 5-Head Teachers, 10-Teachers of Civic Education, 200-Students in Civic Education and 35 Community Members. The target population was 2500, with 250 as sample size. Qualitative data collected from semi-structured interview schedules was analyzed thematically in line with research objectives; while data generated from the questionnaires were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 26) and Microsoft Excel (version 16) to come up with charts, and graphs.

Results: The findings indicated that transformative approaches to teaching and learning civic education have demonstrated significant potential in fostering active citizenship and social responsibility among students. These approaches prioritize critical thinking, participatory learning, and real-world problem-solving, enabling students to engage deeply with civic issues. Experiential learning activities, such as community projects and service learning, have been particularly effective in bridging theoretical knowledge and practical application. Moreover, the integration of technology and digital platforms has enhanced student engagement and accessibility to diverse perspectives.

Recommendation: Schools and members of the community should provide opportunities for students to participate in community projects, advocacy campaigns, or volunteer activities related to civic issues. This practical engagement helps students develop a sense of responsibility and empowerment as active contributors to their communities.

Keywords: Active Learning, Civic Engagement, Inclusivity, Participatory Learning, and Service Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transformative approaches to teaching and learning civic education involve educational strategies designed to deeply engage students in understanding and participating in civic life. These approaches emphasize critical thinking, reflection, and active participation, aiming to empower students to become informed, responsible, and active citizens (Mainde et al, 2022). Transformative pedagogy in civic education encourages learners to question and challenge existing social structures, understand diverse perspectives, and develop the skills needed for civic engagement and social change. Methods often include project-based learning, community involvement, discussions on current events, and the integration of technology to connect students with broader social issues. The goal is to create a learning environment where students not only acquire knowledge about civic institutions and processes but also develop the capacity to apply this knowledge in real-world contexts, fostering a sense of agency and commitment to democratic principles and social justice (Chanda et al, 2024).

Active learning is an instructional approach that actively engages students in the learning process, as opposed to traditional passive methods where students receive information from the instructor without direct interaction. It encompasses a variety of strategies, including collaborative activities, problem-solving tasks, discussions, hands-on experiments, and case studies. Dewey (2011) says that this method emphasizes critical thinking, analysis, and synthesis of information, encouraging students to participate, reflect, and apply their knowledge. Active learning aims to make the educational experience more dynamic and effective by fostering deeper understanding and retention of material, enhancing motivation, and developing skills that are essential for real-world problem-solving and lifelong learning.

Civic engagement refers to the participation of individuals in activities aimed at influencing public policy, governance, and the overall functioning of their communities. It encompasses a broad range of activities, including voting, volunteering, participating in community organizations, attending public meetings, engaging in public debate, and advocating for social or political causes. Civic engagement is fundamental to a functioning democracy, as it empowers citizens to contribute to the decision-making processes that affect their lives. It fosters a sense of responsibility, community, and shared purpose, promoting the development of civic skills and a more informed and active citizenry (Chanda, 2023). Through civic engagement, individuals can influence policies, hold government accountable, and work collectively towards common goals, thereby enhancing the quality of life within their communities.

Inclusivity in teaching refers to the practice of creating an educational environment where all students, regardless of their background, abilities, or identities, feel valued, respected, and supported. This approach recognizes and addresses the diverse needs of students by incorporating various teaching methods, materials, and assessments that cater to different learning styles and abilities (Chondoka, 2010). Inclusivity in teaching involves actively challenging and eliminating barriers to learning, whether they be physical, social, or academic. It encompasses ensuring accessibility for students with disabilities, integrating culturally relevant content, and promoting a

classroom culture that celebrates diversity and encourages open dialogue. By fostering an inclusive classroom, educators aim to provide equal opportunities for all students to succeed and contribute, ultimately enhancing the overall learning experience and outcomes for everyone.

Participatory learning is an educational approach that emphasizes active engagement and collaboration among learners, educators, and sometimes even community members. It focuses on the idea that learning is most effective when individuals are actively involved in the process, rather than passively receiving information. In this model, learners are encouraged to share their perspectives, experiences, and knowledge, which fosters a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This approach often includes group discussions, hands-on activities, problem-solving tasks, and real-world applications (Cruickshank, 2011). By valuing each participant's contribution, participatory learning helps to build a sense of ownership and responsibility towards the learning process, enhances critical thinking skills, and promotes a more democratic and inclusive educational environment. This method is particularly effective in diverse educational settings, as it acknowledges and leverages the unique backgrounds and insights of all participants, ultimately leading to a richer and more comprehensive learning experience.

Service learning is an educational approach that integrates community service with academic coursework, allowing students to apply classroom knowledge to real-world situations. It aims to enhance learning by engaging students in activities that address community needs while fostering civic responsibility and personal growth. Through structured reflection, students connect their service experiences with academic content, leading to a deeper understanding of course material and its practical applications. Chanda (2024) says that service learning benefits communities by providing valuable services and promoting social justice, while students gain hands-on experience, develop critical thinking skills, and cultivate a sense of empathy and social awareness. This experiential learning method bridges the gap between theory and practice, preparing students for active and informed citizenship.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The study on Transformative Approaches to Teaching and Learning Civic Education in selected secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia aims to address the existing gaps and limitations in traditional civic education methods. Alma et al (2024) observed that transformative approaches focus on engaging students more deeply by fostering critical thinking, active participation, and real-world problem-solving skills. This involves innovative teaching strategies that go beyond rote memorization, encouraging students to understand and critically evaluate civic concepts, and apply them in practical contexts (Kantongo et al, 2023). The study seeks to explore how these methods can better prepare students to be informed, responsible citizens who are capable of contributing to the democratic processes and societal development. By examining the implementation and outcomes of these approaches in selected schools, the study aimed to provide insights and recommendations for enhancing civic education in Zambia.

1.3. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to explore and analyze innovative and dynamic methodologies that enhance the teaching and learning of civic education in secondary schools in Lusaka district in Zambia.

1.4. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Investigate the effectiveness of transformative teaching methodologies in enhancing students' understanding and engagement in civic education in Zambian secondary schools.
- Evaluate the impact of transformative learning strategies on students' civic knowledge, skills, and attitudes in Zambian secondary schools.

1.5. Conceptual Framework

The framework centers around integrating critical pedagogy, student-centered learning, and experiential learning methodologies. This framework aims to foster critical thinking, active citizenship, and social responsibility among students. It emphasizes the importance of creating an inclusive and participatory classroom environment where students are encouraged to question and analyze societal structures and issues. By incorporating real-life scenarios and community engagement projects, students can connect theoretical knowledge with practical applications, thus enhancing their understanding and commitment to civic responsibilities (Chanda, 2024). The framework also includes teacher professional development to equip educators with the skills and knowledge necessary to implement these transformative practices effectively. Additionally, it advocates for the use of diverse instructional materials and assessment methods that align with the principles of democratic education and social justice. This approach not only aims to improve academic outcomes but also to empower students to become proactive members of their communities, capable of contributing to the development and betterment of society (Berge, 2017).

1.6. Significance of the Study

The study holds significant importance for several reasons. Firstly, it addresses the critical need for an educational framework that not only imparts knowledge but also fosters critical thinking, active citizenship, and social responsibility among students. By evaluating and implementing transformative pedagogies, the study aims to enhance students' understanding of democratic principles, human rights, and civic duties, which are essential for building a more informed and engaged citizenry. Additionally, this research can provide valuable insights into the current teaching practices and identify gaps or challenges that educators face, thereby offering practical recommendations for curriculum development and teacher training programs. The outcomes of this study have the potential to influence educational policy and practice in Zambia, promoting a more participatory and inclusive approach to civic education. Furthermore, it contributes to the global discourse on educational reforms and the role of education in empowering young people to become proactive members of their communities and society at large.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative data. Exploratory and descriptive designs were as well considered appropriate as they also allowed for more flexible strategies of data collection in order to respond to research objectives (Banda et al, 2017). The study was conducted in 5 selected secondary schools of Lusaka district, targeting 5-Head Teachers, 10-Teachers of Civic Education, 200-Students in Civic Education and 35 Community Members. The target population was 2500, with 250 as sample size (10% of the target population). Qualitative data collected from semi-structured interview schedules was analyzed thematically in line with research objectives; while data generated from the questionnaires were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 26) and Microsoft Excel (version 16) to come up with charts, and graphs. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

3.1. The Effectiveness of Transformative Teaching Methodologies in Enhancing Students' Understanding and Engagement in Civic Education in Zambian Secondary Schools

Study results revealed that enhancing students' understanding and engagement in civic education in Zambian secondary schools through transformative teaching methodologies involves several innovative approaches. Service Learning was at 20%, Critical Thinking Development at 15%, Technology Integration at 10%, Collaborative Learning at 20%, Culturally Relevant Teaching at 10%, Student-Centered Approaches at 20%, and Active Learning Strategies at 5%. Figure1 below summarized the findings;

Figure 1: Transformative Teaching Methodologies in Enhancing Students' Understanding and Engagement in Civic Education

The study results noted that service learning is increasingly recognized as a powerful transformative teaching methodology in Zambian secondary schools, particularly in civic education. By integrating classroom learning with community service activities, Service Learning not only enhances students' understanding of civic responsibilities but also fosters active engagement in addressing local societal issues (Chanda, 2024). Students participate in meaningful projects that directly benefit their communities, such as environmental conservation initiatives or community health campaigns. Through these experiences, students develop a deeper appreciation for civic values, critical thinking skills, and empathy towards diverse community needs. Service Learning thus cultivates a sense of civic duty and empowers students to become proactive citizens who contribute positively to society (Mainde & Chola, 2020). Civic education teachers added that critical thinking encourages students to analyze information, question assumptions, and evaluate evidence, fostering a deeper comprehension of civic concepts. The respondents expressed that:

“By incorporating active learning strategies such as debates, case studies, and simulations, educators can create opportunities for students to apply critical thinking skills to real-world civic issues”.

Furthermore, integrating service learning into civic education allows students to connect classroom learning with community engagement. Through service learning projects, students actively participate in addressing local issues, gaining firsthand experience of civic responsibilities and challenges. This approach not only enhances their understanding of civic concepts but also cultivates a sense of civic duty and empathy towards community needs (Chanda, 2023). Moreover, promoting dialogue and encouraging diverse perspectives in classroom discussions stimulates critical thinking among students. By analyzing different viewpoints and engaging in respectful debate, students develop the ability to consider multiple angles of complex civic issues, fostering informed decision-making and active citizenship.

The head teachers alluded that technology integration in civic education in Zambian secondary schools serves as a transformative teaching methodology by enhancing both student understanding and engagement. Chanda & Zohaib (2024) added that through the strategic use of technology such as interactive simulations, multimedia presentations, and online resources, educators can contextualize civic concepts within students' everyday lives, fostering deeper comprehension. Interactive platforms and digital tools enable students to explore complex civic issues actively, encouraging critical thinking and collaborative problem-solving. Additionally, technology facilitates real-time access to current events and diverse perspectives, promoting informed citizenship and civic participation (Dewey, 2017). By leveraging technology, Zambian educators can effectively cultivate students' civic awareness and responsibility, preparing them to actively contribute to their communities and society at large.

The respondents added that student-centered approaches in civic education have shown transformative potential in Zambian secondary schools by placing students at the center of learning. Mainde et al (2022)'s study noted that these methodologies, such as project-based learning and service learning, actively engage students in real-world civic issues, fostering a deeper understanding of democratic principles and community responsibilities. One of the respondents explained that:

“By encouraging active participation, critical thinking, and collaboration, these approaches not only enhance academic learning but also empower students to become active citizens capable of contributing meaningfully to their communities and society at large”.

The respondents observed that by fostering peer interaction and teamwork, students can actively participate in discussions, problem-solving, and decision-making processes related to civic issues. This approach not only cultivates critical thinking and communication skills but also promotes a deeper understanding of democratic principles and civic responsibilities (Finkel, 2011). Through collaborative learning, students can develop empathy, tolerance, and a sense of civic duty, preparing them to become active and informed citizens in their communities and beyond.

Civic education students stated that active learning strategies are pivotal in transforming the teaching methodologies particularly in civic education. By actively involving them in their learning process through techniques like debates, simulations, and group discussions, educators can foster deeper

understanding and heightened engagement. Such methods not only cultivate critical thinking and problem-solving skills but also encourage students to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world civic issues, thereby preparing them as informed and active participants in their communities. This approach not only enhances academic outcomes but also nurtures a sense of civic responsibility and engagement among students, shaping them into proactive citizens of tomorrow's Zambia (Chanda, 2024). Furthermore, community members added that Culturally Relevant Teaching (CRT) is a transformative methodology that holds significant promise in enhancing students' understanding and engagement in civic education within Zambian secondary schools. By integrating culturally significant content, experiences, and perspectives into the curriculum, CRT not only acknowledges but also values students' diverse backgrounds and identities (Banda & Mpolomoka, 2018). This approach fosters a deeper connection between classroom learning and students' lived experiences, thereby making civic education more relevant and meaningful. Furthermore, CRT encourages critical thinking and active participation by empowering students to explore and analyze societal issues from multiple cultural lenses, ultimately preparing them to become informed and engaged citizens in their communities (Brandon, 2008). These methodologies can help foster a deeper understanding of civic education among students and encourage active participation in civic life both within and beyond the school environment.

3.2. The Impact of Transformative Learning Strategies on Students' Civic Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes in Zambian Secondary Schools

The study findings on objective 2 noted that the impact of transformative learning strategies on students' civic knowledge, skills, and attitudes in Zambian secondary schools can be profound. Transformative learning focuses on deep personal reflection and critical thinking, often challenging existing beliefs and perspectives. Promote Active Citizenship at 35%, Enhance Civic Knowledge was at 25%, Foster Positive Civic Attitudes at 25%, and the least was Develop Civic Skills at 15%.

The study results revealed that promoting active citizenship through transformative learning strategies in Zambian secondary schools can significantly enhance students' civic knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Transformative learning fosters critical thinking and reflection, encouraging students to analyze societal issues and engage actively in their communities. One of the community members explained that:

“By integrating real-world problems into the curriculum, students develop a deeper understanding of civic responsibilities and the importance of civic engagement. These strategies often involve experiential learning, such as community service projects or simulations of democratic processes, which allow students to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations”.

Through these activities, students not only learn about governance structures and civic rights but also develop practical skills in communication, teamwork, and leadership. CDC (2010) recorded that transformative learning encourages empathy and understanding of diverse perspectives,

which are crucial for effective citizenship in a multicultural society like Zambia. Chanda (2023) supported this finding by stating that by challenging preconceptions and fostering open dialogue, these strategies empower students to become proactive agents of change, advocating for social justice and participating actively in decision-making processes within their communities.

Civic education teachers pointed out that transformative learning strategies play a crucial role in fostering positive civic attitudes among students in Zambian secondary schools. These strategies emphasize critical reflection, experiential learning, and active participation in community and civic activities. One key impact is the development of a heightened awareness of civic responsibilities and rights among students (Guttman, 2017). Through activities such as community service projects and simulations of civic processes, students gain practical insights into their roles as active citizens. This experience not only enhances their understanding of civic issues but also cultivates a sense of agency in addressing societal challenges. Furthermore, transformative learning encourages empathy and tolerance by exposing students to diverse perspectives and social issues within their communities. This exposure helps in breaking down stereotypes and promotes a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity and social justice issues (Mainde et al, 2021). Moreover, these strategies promote skills such as critical thinking, communication, and collaboration, which are essential for effective civic engagement. Students learn to analyze complex civic problems, articulate their views persuasively, and work collaboratively to achieve common goals.

Furthermore, the respondents alluded that enhancing civic knowledge through transformative learning strategies involves implementing innovative educational approaches that go beyond traditional classroom teaching. These strategies aim to deepen students' understanding of civic concepts, foster critical thinking, and encourage active participation in civic life. One of the teachers expressed that:

“One effective method is integrating service learning into the curriculum, where students engage in community-based projects that address real societal issues. By applying classroom learning to practical situations, students not only acquire theoretical knowledge but also develop practical skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, and communication”.

Furthermore, fostering an inclusive classroom environment that respects diverse viewpoints and encourages dialogue is crucial. This approach cultivates students' ability to engage in constructive debates, understand different perspectives on civic issues, and develop empathy towards others. Additionally, leveraging technology and multimedia tools can enhance civic education by making abstract concepts more accessible and engaging. Interactive simulations, online discussions, and digital platforms can provide students with opportunities to explore complex civic issues and collaborate with peers beyond the classroom walls (M’cormack, 2011). Lastly, promoting active citizenship through extracurricular activities such as debates, mock elections, and community service initiatives helps students apply their learning in real-world contexts. These experiences

empower students to become informed, responsible citizens who are equipped to contribute positively to their communities and participate actively in democratic processes (CDE, 2016). The head teachers observed that transformative learning strategies have shown significant potential in enhancing students' civic knowledge, skills, and attitudes. These strategies, such as service learning, experiential learning, and reflective practices, play a crucial role in developing civic skills among students (Barber, 2004). Service learning, for instance, integrates community service with academic learning objectives, providing students with real-world experiences that deepen their understanding of civic responsibilities. Through active participation in community projects, students not only apply theoretical knowledge but also cultivate empathy, leadership, and collaboration skills essential for civic engagement (Chanda, 2023). Experiential learning approaches, including simulations, role-playing, and field trips, immerse students in practical scenarios where they explore civic issues firsthand. This hands-on experience enables them to grasp the complexities of civic life, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving abilities needed to address societal challenges. Reflective practices, integral to transformative learning, encourage students to analyze their civic experiences, beliefs, and actions. By reflecting on their roles as active citizens, students develop a deeper awareness of social issues and their personal responsibilities within the community (Ehman & Glenn, 2004). This introspective process nurtures self-efficacy and a sense of civic duty, motivating students to contribute positively to society. The implementation of these transformative learning strategies not only enhances students' civic knowledge but also empowers them to become informed, engaged citizens. By equipping students with civic skills through experiential learning and reflective practices, educators can cultivate a generation of young leaders committed to addressing local and global challenges for sustainable societal progress. Chanda (2023) noted that in Zambia, integrating transformative learning into civic education could help address challenges such as civic apathy and lack of active participation among youth. It aligns with efforts to promote democratic values, social justice, and sustainable development goals.

Figure 2: Impact of Transformative Learning Strategies on Students' Civic Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the implementation of transformative approaches to teaching and learning civic education in secondary schools in Lusaka District has demonstrated significant potential in fostering holistic student development. By integrating experiential learning, community engagement, and critical reflection into the curriculum, educators have successfully enhanced students' understanding of civic issues and their role in society. This approach not only enriches academic knowledge but also cultivates essential civic skills such as critical thinking, empathy, and active citizenship. Moreover, the transformative pedagogies employed have shown promise in addressing socio-economic disparities among students, fostering inclusivity, and promoting social justice awareness. Through service-learning projects and real-world applications of civic concepts, students have been empowered to apply their learning in meaningful ways, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical civic engagement. Furthermore, the positive outcomes observed underscore the importance of continuous professional development for teachers and ongoing support from educational stakeholders. These elements are crucial for

sustaining the effectiveness of transformative approaches in civic education, ensuring that they remain responsive to evolving societal needs and educational priorities. As Zambia navigates its path towards enhancing civic education in secondary schools, embracing transformative teaching methodologies offers a viable pathway to nurturing informed, active, and responsible citizens. By nurturing a generation equipped with both knowledge and a sense of civic duty, these approaches contribute to the broader goal of building a more participatory and democratic society.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

- Teachers of civic education should incorporate experiential learning methods such as service learning, simulations, debates, and role-playing activities. These methods allow students to engage directly with civic issues, fostering a deeper understanding of their roles as active citizens.
- Teachers of civic education should emphasize critical thinking skills by encouraging students to analyze and evaluate civic issues from multiple perspectives. Reflection exercises can help students connect their learning to real-life situations, enhancing their ability to apply civic knowledge.
- Schools and members of the community should provide opportunities for students to participate in community projects, advocacy campaigns, or volunteer activities related to civic issues. This practical engagement helps students develop a sense of responsibility and empowerment as active contributors to their communities.
- Schools should create a classroom environment that encourages open dialogue, respectful debate, and the exchange of diverse viewpoints. This approach promotes civic discourse and tolerance for differing opinions, essential for democratic participation.

REFERENCES

- Alma, V. L., Zohaib, H. S., Oki, D., Chanda, C. T., & Moses, A. A. (2024). Revolutionary Teaching Approaches: Exploring the Educational Landscape in Pakistan via Outcome-Based Education. *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Research*, Volume 3, Issue 2, 73-79, May 2024, Available: <https://journal.aira.or.id/index.php/jistr/>, ISSN: 2828-2973.
- Banda S, & Mpolomoka, D. L. (2018). Culturally Relevant Education and Training for Communities: A review. *African Educational Research Journal*. 2018;6(2): 88-93. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30918/AERJ.62.18.019>.
- Banda, S., Mpolomoka, D. L., Mbono, D., & Sampa, R.L (2017). "Use of Questions in Qualitative Research: How Questions Guided Our Study", *International Journal of Development Research*, 7, (12), 17895-17898, Available: <http://www.journalijdr.com>, ISSN: 2230-9926.
- Barber, B. (2004). *Strong Democracy: Participatory Politics for A New Age*. Berkeley, University of California Press.
- Berge, A. (2017). *Learning Citizenship in Democracy*. A Resource Book. Balaka. Montfortmedia.
- Brandon, M. (2008). *The Role of Civic Education: A Forth coming Education Policy Task Force Position Paper from the Communitarian Network*, Washington.
- Chanda. C. T. (2023). Effects of Civic Education on Learners' Response to Governance Tenets: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Kitwe District of Copperbelt Province, Zambia. *Global Scientific Journals*, Volume 12, Issue 4, 112-131, April 2024, Available: www.globalscientificjournals.com, ISSN 2320-9186.
- Chanda. C. T. (2023). Academic and Political Challenges Faced by Teachers in The Teaching of Civic Education: A case of selected secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 4, no 8, pp 3309-3316, August 2023, Available: www.ijrpr.com, ISSN 2582-7421.
- Chanda. C. T. (2023). Challenges Encountered in the Teaching and Learning of Civic Education: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Solwezi District of North-Western Province, Zambia. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, Volume 05, Issue 09, 610-621, September 2023, Available: www.irjmets.com, <https://doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS44613>.

Chanda, C.T. (2023). Effects of Civic Education on Learners' Decision-Making: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 4, no 11, pp 409-417, November 2023, Available: www.ijrpr.com, ISSN 2582-7421.

Chanda, C.T. (2023). Civic Education and Conflict Resolutions: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Kitwe District of Copperbelt Province, Zambia. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 19(03), 1035-1043, September 2023, Available: <https://wjarr.com/>, <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.19.3.1923>. eISSN: 2581-9615.

Chanda, C.T. (2024). "Service Learning and Civic Engagement: Exploring the Linkages". *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 5, no 4, pp 7056-7064, April 2024, Available: www.ijrpr.com, ISSN 2582-7421.

Chanda, C.T. (2024). Civic Education and Citizen Participation in Local Governance: A Case of Lusaka District, Zambia. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Volume 5, Issue 3, 4628-4637, March 2024, www.ijrpr.com, ISSN 2582-7421.

Chanda, C. T. (2024). Civic Education and National Development: A Comprehensive Analysis of Zambia. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, Volume 50, Issue 6, Page 170-190; Available: <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i61404>, Article no. AJESS.116901, ISSN: 2581-6268.

Chanda. C. T., Mainde, D., & Chisebe, S. (2024). Promoting Democratic Values Through Civic Education: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 22(03), 586-597, June 2024, Available: <https://wjarr.com/>, <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.3.1664>.

Chanda. C. T., & Zohaib, H. S. (2024). "Harnessing Information Communication Technology in Civic Education Teaching and Learning: A Comprehensive Review". *Global Scientific Journals*, Volume 12, Issue 4, 112-131, April 2024, Available: www.globalscientificjournals.com, ISSN 2320-9186.

Chondoka, A. Y. et al. (2010). Civic Education Teachers Manual. Lusaka. ZEPH.

Cogan, J. (2006). Citizenship for the List Century. An International Perspective on Education. Kogan Page. London.

Cruickshank, R. (2011). The Art of Teaching. New York. McGraw- Hill.

Curriculum Development Centre. (2010). Zambia Basic Education Curriculum for Grade 8 and 9. Civic Education Syllabus. Lusaka. CDC.

- Department of Curriculum Development and Evaluation. (2016). Botswana Social Studies Teaching Methods. A Resource Book for Teachers. Gaborone. Macmillan.
- Dewey, J. (2017). School and Society. Chicago. University of Chicago Press.
- Dewey, J. (2011). Democracy and Education. Newyork. The Free Press.
- Ehman, L. & Glenn, A. (2004). Interactive Technology in Social Studies. New York. Macmillan.
- Finkel, S. (2011). Adult Civic Education and the Development of the Democratic Political. Washington. DC. World Bank.
- Guttman, A. (2017). Democratic Education with a New Preface and Epilogue. Princeton. Princeton University Press.
- Kantongo, M. et. al. (2013). Civic Education in Norwegian and Zambian Schools. Lusaka. Unza Press.
- Kincheloe, J. L. (2007). Critical pedagogy. New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Lawry, L. & Van, A. (2016). Liberal education and civic engagement. New York, NY: Ford Foundation.
- Mainde, & Chola, D. (2020). The Teaching of Civic Education in Zambian Secondary Schools as a Strategy for Effective Political Participation. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, |Volume IV, Issue XII, 293-301, December 2020, Available: <http://www.rsisinternational.org/>, |ISSN 2454-6186.
- Mainde, D., Chola, D. K., and Mpolomoka, D. L. (2021). Interrogating Civic Education Pedagogies that Stimulate Political Participation in Selected Secondary Schools in Zambia. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, Volume V, Issue II, 269-279, February 2021, Available: <http://www.rsisinternational.org/>, |ISSN 2454-6186.
- Mainde, D., Mpolomoka, D. L., and Mwansa, M. (2022). Localizing Integrative Approaches in Civic Education: Towards development of Moral and Civic Competencies of Secondary School Learners. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, |Volume VI, Issue I, 588-596, January 2022, Available: <http://www.rsisinternational.org/>, |ISSN 2454-6186.
- Mainde, D., Mtonga, D. E., Magasu, O., & Mpolomoka, D. L. (2022). Examining Civic Education Learning and Assessment Strategies in Selected Secondary Schools in Zambia. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, Volume 49, Issue 1, Page 42-52, September 2023, Available: DOI: 10.9734/AJESS/2023/v49i11099, Article no. AJESS.106456, ISSN: 2581-6268.
- M'cormack. F. (2011). Approaches to Civic Education in Africa. UK. University.

Author's Short Biography

Chanda Chansa Thelma specializes in Political and Social Sciences, as well as Education. She has lectured and still lecturing at the University level under the school of Humanities and Education.